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Environmental influences on children's active travel: a spatial analysis of school routes

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how the built environment influences children's physical activity during school travel and within school neighborhoods in Olomouc, Czechia. The dataset combines accelerometer-measured activity, manually mapped routes, and GIS-based environmental indicators. Data from 161 eighth-grade pupils across ten primary schools were analyzed using 25 m route buffers and 500 m network service areas around schools. Variables included building height, pedestrian infrastructure, traffic intensity, greenery, noise, and traffic accidents. Active school travel was positively associated with sidewalk area, traffic intensity, building height, and traffic accidents, revealing accessibility benefits and exposure risks in compact urban settings. Total daily activity and sleep were not significantly related to environmental factors. The study shows that the built environment shapes active school mobility, whereas overall activity patterns depend mainly on individual and social routines. Integrating ActiGraph accelerometer and spatial data offers an innovative approach for analyzing children's mobility in medium-sized European cities.

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Active transport; children; GIS; spatial analysis; environment

1. Introduction

Physical inactivity among children is one of the most pressing global health concerns of the twenty-first century. According to the World Health Organization, fewer than one in five children worldwide meet the recommendation of at least 60 min of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) per day, while sedentary time and obesity rates continue to rise. The consequences of insufficient physical activity during childhood include increased risks of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and impaired cognitive and psychosocial development in later life (Althoff et al., 2025; Nigg et al., 2024). One of the most practical and sustainable strategies to integrate movement into children's daily lives is active school travel (AST) (walking or cycling to and from school), which contributes substantially to overall daily MVPA (Rojas Lopez & Wong, 2017; Vorlíček et al., 2025; Wex et al., 2023).

Despite its health and environmental benefits, the share of children using active modes to school has declined significantly over the past decades. Several studies have documented this downward trend, often attributing it to increasing car dependency, urban sprawl, parental safety concerns, and the absence of safe pedestrian infrastructure (Carver et al., 2019; Dalton et al., 2011; Wong et al., 2011). Recent reviews indicate that this decline has been

observed across many high-income countries worldwide, often linked to parental safety concerns, increased car availability, and changing travel habits (Aranda-Balboa et al., 2020; Vorlíček et al., 2025). In the Central European context, similar tendencies have been reported: recent analyses in Czechia and Slovakia indicate that fewer than half of children regularly walk or cycle to school, while motorized transport dominates especially in suburban zones (Dygrýn et al., 2015). A recent study based on HBSC data further confirms a long-term decline in active school transport among Czech adolescents between 2006 and 2022 (Vorlíček et al., 2025).

A substantial body of literature has examined the relationship between the built environment and AST. Determinants repeatedly identified as significant include distance to school, street-network connectivity, intersection density, sidewalk availability, traffic exposure, and green-space accessibility (Broberg et al., 2013; Carver et al., 2019; Dalton et al., 2011; Wangzom et al., 2023). Systematic reviews (Savolainen et al., 2024; Wong et al., 2011) have confirmed that shorter distances, higher walkability, and safer crossings strongly increase the likelihood of active commuting, whereas high traffic intensity or lack of pedestrian infrastructure act as barriers. Nevertheless, results regarding the influence of greenery and open space remain mixed: while

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some studies report positive effects of vegetation and park proximity on children's walking and cycling (Khanian et al., 2024), others found only indirect or context-specific relationships (Campos-Garzón et al., 2024).

Active transportation to school (AST) is strongly shaped by characteristics of the built environment, including route safety, pedestrian infrastructure, traffic conditions, and neighborhood design, which can either facilitate or constrain children's opportunities to walk or cycle to school (Panter et al., 2008; Timperio et al., 2006). Among environmental determinants, distance between home and school consistently emerges as the most influential factor in children's travel mode choice, with shorter distances substantially increasing the likelihood of active commuting (Larsen et al., 2012; McDonald, 2008).

Parallel to these thematic findings, methodological advances have shifted attention from zonal to route-based assessments of children's environmental exposure. Early studies typically relied on circular buffers (e.g. 300–800 m) around homes or schools to approximate spatial conditions (Crooks et al., 2021; Jacobs et al., 2021). More recent research has adopted along-route analysis, measuring environmental attributes directly along individual travel paths. Dessing et al. (2016) demonstrated that children's real GPS-tracked routes differ considerably from the shortest network paths, particularly in land-use composition and traffic exposure. Stewart et al. (2017) compared on-line mapped and GPS-recorded routes among adolescents and found high agreement (within 50 m) in both geometry and environmental indicators when narrow buffers were applied. Similarly, Helbich et al. (2016) confirmed that route-specific metrics explain AST behavior better than zone-based averages. In our analysis, the 25 m buffer therefore serves only to delineate the immediate corridor surrounding each mapped route rather than representing a zonal neighborhood unit.

Recent years have also brought growing integration of accelerometer, GPS, and GIS data in physical-activity research (Hunter et al., 2024). This enables linking objectively measured activity intensity with spatially explicit environmental indicators. However, such integrative studies remain rare, and almost none combine accelerometer-based MVPA, mapped school routes, and multi-source environmental datasets within a single analytical model.

An additional research challenge concerns the dual nature of the urban environment. While high-density areas with good sidewalk infrastructure may facilitate walking and cycling, they also expose children to greater noise, air pollution, and traffic-related injury risk (Broberg & Sarjala, 2015; Ross et al., 2020). Studies in Finland and the Netherlands (Helbich, 2017; Sarjala et al., 2016) have documented strong spatial clustering of environmental risk factors – dense traffic, limited

greenery, and high accident frequency – within central urban zones. Conversely, suburban environments often provide greener surroundings but lower connectivity and longer travel distances, leading to decreased AST participation.

Given the limited number of studies integrating accelerometer-based activity data, mapped school routes, and detailed environmental indicators within a single analytical framework, and providing their spatial visualization, there is a need for research that integrates behavioral and environmental data at multiple spatial scales. This study therefore investigates how environmental characteristics along school travel routes and within school neighborhoods influence children's physical activity levels in the city of Olomouc, Czechia. Using detailed GIS data and accelerometer-based activity records, the study evaluates associations between pedestrian infrastructure, traffic intensity, greenery, and noise exposure, and examines differences between route-level and neighborhood-level effects. Furthermore, it explores how movement during school travel relates to total daily MVPA and sleep indicators, as recorded by ActiGraph accelerometers.

The **main hypothesis** of this study is that children attending schools located in more walkable, infrastructure-rich, and densely built urban areas exhibit higher levels of MVPA during school travel. In contrast, overall daily physical activity levels (MVPA accumulated across the entire day) and accelerometer-derived sleep indicators are expected to show weaker associations with environmental factors, as these broader behavioral patterns are influenced by a wider range of individual and social factors beyond the immediate travel environment. The study seeks to provide spatially explicit evidence linking behavioral data and environmental exposure, thereby supporting local policy measures aimed at promoting safe and active mobility among schoolchildren.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area

The city of Olomouc, with a population of 102,293 in 2024 and an area of 103.33 km², is the sixth-largest city in Czechia. Olomouc follows a nearly monocentric urban pattern with a centripetal transport structure. The historical core serves as a pedestrian zone encircled by green parks, promoting walking and offering safe routes for schoolchildren (Burian et al., 2020). Commuting forms a major component of urban mobility. Each day, 5,656 children commute to school within Olomouc, while the total number of school commuters reaches 14,017 (Czech Statistical Office, 2021). In Olomouc, there are 25 elementary schools established by the city, with a total capacity

of approximately 10,500 places, attended by more than 9,300 pupils (City of Olomouc, 2024).

2.2. Data

The data for this study were collected as part of the Safe Journey to School project, which the city of Olomouc has been implementing since 2019. The project combined several data collection components, including mapping of school routes, a questionnaire survey among pupils, and accelerometer-based monitoring of physical activity. All 25 primary schools were invited to participate, and pupils from 15 schools took part in the survey (a total of 1,013 pupils). Data was collected through a web-based mapping application, which consisted of two parts. Firstly, respondents marked problems in the school surroundings and their approximate route to school on the map. In total, 828 individual routes were mapped and visualized through the web map application (Figure 1). Secondly, students answered selected questions (e.g. mode of travel to school, sense of safety, etc.). The mapping activity was typically conducted during regular school classes in computer classrooms using a standardized online application with instructions for students. This process yielded a total of 1,945 reported problems, which were then evaluated by city officials (Burian & Šramo, 2024). The questionnaire results were statistically analyzed and provided to city staff in the form of a research report (Olomouc City Chief Architect's Office, 2024).

For the purpose of monitoring active mobility, we focused on eighth-grade students in Olomouc, deliberately selecting 10 of the city's 25 primary schools for accelerometer monitoring to maximize variability in geographic location, school size, and surrounding environmental characteristics (Figure 2). The selected schools represent different parts of the city and different types of urban school environments. In total, 15 schools participated in the broader Safe Journey to School survey, which provided route-mapping and questionnaire data used in parts of the spatial analysis. Participants were equipped by a wrist-worn ActiGraph accelerometer, along with a usage log, a one-week travel diary, and detailed instructions. Using this procedure, data on physical activity behaviors (one week) were obtained from 161 respondents. Accelerometer monitoring was conducted in a subset of schools where sufficient numbers of pupils and teachers agreed to participate, focusing on pupils in the 8th and 9th grades due to the limited number of available devices. Further processing of the accelerometer data provided detailed information on daily activity patterns, including sleep duration and efficiency, sedentary behavior (SB), light (LPA), moderate (MPA), and vigorous (VPA) physical activity (Migueles et al., 2019). To evaluate the factors influencing students' active travel to school, spatial data from the databases listed in Table 1 were used.

The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Faculty of Physical Culture, Palacký University Olomouc, ensuring compliance with ethical standards for research involving human participants (Approval No. 20/2023, 24 March 2023). Participants were not offered financial compensation for their participation.

2.3. Data processing

The primary objective of the data processing phase was to integrate three complementary datasets – accelerometer records, questionnaire responses, and mapped school routes – in order to analyze the environmental factors influencing children's active travel. The analytical workflow therefore consisted of several steps, including route processing, derivation of environmental indicators along routes and within school surroundings, and subsequent statistical analyses linking these environmental variables with behavioral indicators derived from accelerometer data. The rationale of these steps was to quantify environmental exposure during school travel and to examine its relationship with physical activity patterns. The initial data processing was conducted in Microsoft Excel, followed by advanced spatial analyses performed in GIS environments (ArcGIS Pro and QGIS), and followed by statistical analysis in RStudio.

Accelerometer data were processed using standard procedures commonly applied in ActiGraph-based physical activity research (Migueles et al., 2019). From the raw accelerometer records, several behavioral indicators were derived, including moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA), sleep duration, and sleep efficiency. MVPA represents the total time spent in moderate and vigorous physical activity accumulated during the day. Sleep indicators were derived from the detected sleep period time and related sleep metrics. For the statistical analysis, aggregated indicators for school days (Monday–Friday) were used.

2.3.1. Processing of school route data

In the first stage, the line layer representing individual school routes was carefully reviewed and edited to ensure spatial accuracy and consistency. The processing involved several manual and automated steps aimed at removing invalid or incomplete records, adjusting route geometry, and aligning all paths with the pedestrian network. Subsequently, all valid routes were snapped to the pedestrian network to achieve topological consistency. The snapping procedure was carried out in QGIS using the Snap Geometries tool, first aligning the route endpoints with school entrances and then connecting entire route lines to the nearest pedestrian network segments. Finally, a manual post-processing step was performed to correct any incorrectly snapped routes. Significant change in the geometrical quality between source and corrected routes is visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 1. Example of the map application with individual routes and reported problems.

To evaluate the spatial concentration of school routes and identify sections most frequently used by students, all mapped paths were further processed

into route segments. This approach enabled the identification of the most intensively used pedestrian corridors within the city, providing valuable input

Figure 2. Overview map of basic schools in Olomouc involved in the study (Lines represent individual routes with partial transparency; darker segments indicate locations where multiple routes overlap.).

Table 1. Overview of spatial data used for GIS analysis.

Dataset	Source	Year
Pedestrian network	OpenStreetMap	2024
Traffic accidents	Czech Police	2017–2024
Public transport stops	OpenStreetMap	2024
Buildings (height, type, category)	State Administration of Land Surveying and Cadaster (Register of Territorial Identification, Addresses and Real Estate)	2024
Traffic intensity	City of Olomouc (City Traffic Model)	2024
Sidewalks	City of Olomouc (Transport Register)	2024
Noise	Ministry of Health (Noise Map)	2022
Green areas	Sentinel (Copernicus)	2021
Greenery – trees	City of Olomouc (Greenery Register)	2024
Primary schools	Ministry of Education (School Register)	2024

for subsequent analyses of route safety, environmental exposure, and accessibility.

2.3.2. Environmental data processing

In the next step, thematic spatial datasets were processed to derive selected environmental characteristics (building height, traffic exposure, sidewalk coverage, greenery composition, and noise levels) associated with each school route. These indicators were selected to represent key aspects of the built environment relevant to active school travel, including pedestrian infrastructure, traffic exposure, and environmental quality. For every route, variables were calculated within a 25 m buffer zone, representing the immediate surroundings of the student's path to school.

In addition to route-level indicators, environmental characteristics were also assessed in the immediate surroundings of each school. This allowed for a consistent comparison between the physical environment along students' individual routes and the broader neighborhood context around each school. Following accessibility standards commonly used in urban planning, a 500 m network service area along the pedestrian network was defined for each school, representing the typical walking catchment area. These two spatial perspectives allow comparison between environmental exposure experienced directly along school routes and broader environmental characteristics of school neighborhoods.

In order to compare schools, all indicators were standardized using min–max normalization and scaled to a 0–10 range. For indicators representing favorable conditions for pedestrian mobility (e.g. sidewalk coverage or greenery), higher values correspond to more favorable environments. For indicators representing potential risk factors (e.g. traffic accidents, traffic intensity, and noise exposure), the scale was reversed so that higher scores indicate more favorable conditions (i.e. lower exposure to risk). For each school, individual indicator scores were then summed to obtain a composite total score of the school's surrounding environment. This indicator-based scoring

represents a comparative evaluation of the spatial conditions at each school and provides a structured basis for subsequent analyses linking school environment characteristics to pupils' travel mode choice.

2.3.3. Statistical analysis

Subsequently, these environmental and behavioral variables were analyzed statistically in R software. First, environmental and behavioral variables were subjected to correlation analysis, whereby the correlation coefficient was calculated, and independence tests were performed. Normality of variables was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test. As several variables violated the assumption of normal distribution, a non-parametric approach was adopted and correlations were calculated using Spearman's rank coefficient. The results of the correlation analysis are presented in correlation matrices, including the indication of statistically insignificant relationships (Rypl et al., 2024). The matrices were compiled for two movement types (overall vs. active) and across two spatial contexts (travel to school vs. school surroundings).

While environmental characteristics are assumed to influence active school travel, children's habitual activity patterns may also predispose them toward particular travel behaviors. To explore whether distinct behavioral profiles exist across schools – independent of environmental gradients – a clustering analysis based on activity and sleep indicators was conducted. As part of the statistical data processing, cluster analysis was conducted to identify homogeneous groups of students within individual schools based on their lifestyle and physical activity level (MVPA during transportation to school, MVPA adjusted to 24 h, sleep efficiency, total sleep hours on school days, and total wakefulness time). Prior to clustering, principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to eliminate multicollinearity among variables, reduce dimensionality, and enhance the robustness of the clustering process.

The analysis used standardized variables aggregated at the school level by computing average values. Based on the eigenvalue scree plot and Kaiser's criterion (eigenvalue > 1), two principal components were retained. These components explained more than 70% of the total variance, indicating sufficient information representation.

Subsequently, k-means cluster analysis was conducted. The optimal number of clusters was determined using the silhouette criterion. Although the highest silhouette score indicated a two-cluster solution, this only distinguished between generally low and high values of the indicators. Therefore, a three-cluster model – also ranked among the top solutions – was selected as a more interpretable representation of population heterogeneity while maintaining acceptable cluster validity. The results are presented using a

Figure 3. Original (left) and corrected (right) routes visualized by the count of lines.

component score plot with cluster membership indicated for each school.

3. Results

3.1. Indicator-based assessment of school surroundings

The quality of the immediate school environment according to a set of indicators capturing pedestrian infrastructure, greenery, traffic safety, traffic intensity and noise exposure, is shown in the [Table 2](#). The total school scores are primarily determined by a combined effect of pedestrian-infrastructure qualities (sidewalks; greenery) and traffic-safety conditions (traffic accidents; traffic intensity in the immediate surroundings). The highest-scoring schools are characterized by favorable values across both domains – they either possess sufficiently dimensioned and adequately maintained pedestrian space, or they are located in areas with relatively low traffic-related risk exposure.

The mid-range scores (~30–38 points) represent a group of schools that do not exhibit extreme values in any of the indicators but likewise lack a clearly outstanding parameter. They can therefore be understood as ‘baseline’ urban street settings, where environmental quality is not the outcome of intentional spatial intervention but rather the cumulative result of fragmented, path-dependent characteristics of place.

In contrast, the lowest-scoring schools share a deficit in at least one foundational precondition of safe and comfortable walking access – typically the absence of adequate sidewalks, or very high exposure to a traffic stressor (crash incidence, intensity, noise). These results confirm that the scoring does not behave as a linearly ‘compensable’ construct: an extremely negative value in one critical category strongly depresses the overall result, regardless of above-average values in other indicators.

Taken together, the aggregated score in this dataset reflects the core environmental determinants of safe everyday child mobility. Aesthetic or partial-comfort attributes (e.g. greenery) have a secondary effect and

Table 2. Indicator scores and total scores for all involved schools.

School	Indicator scores (0–10 points; worst–best)						Total score
	Sidewalks	Buildings	Greenery	Traffic accidents	Traffic intensity	Noise	
Dvorského	0.1	9.8	10.0	9.8	8.5	10.0	48.1
Demlova*	5.6	7.9	7.6	8.1	8.9	7.5	45.7
Raisova*	0.0	10.0	5.7	10.0	10.0	7.5	43.2
Stupkova*	9.5	7.0	4.5	5.9	7.4	3.3	37.5
Svatoplukova	2.5	7.6	1.8	9.3	8.9	5.9	36.0
Tererovo Square	10.0	6.6	4.9	5.8	5.6	1.8	34.8
Holice	8.4	9.4	5.1	6.7	2.7	1.8	34.1
Heyrovského	2.8	6.6	3.4	8.6	8.7	3.6	33.6
Zolova*	0.5	8.9	3.8	8.8	6.6	4.8	33.4
Helsinská	7.1	7.1	5.1	5.6	4.8	1.5	31.3
Mozartova	8.0	6.4	3.3	5.3	4.6	2.7	30.3
Nedvědova	9.9	9.0	4.8	4.1	0.0	0.0	27.8
Spojenců	9.7	2.2	3.1	0.5	6.2	3.5	25.2
Komenium	9.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.9	4.8	20.9

*Schools without ActiGraph measurements (included in the route-mapping survey only).

are not, on their own, sufficient to yield high total scores.

3.2. Environmental influences on physical activity during school travel

Initial correlation analyses focusing on all school-related movements within the wider school surroundings showed only weak and mostly statistically non-significant associations between physical activity and environmental indicators, suggesting that overall transportation behavior does not adequately capture patterns specific to active commuting. Because total transportation behavior may mask patterns specific to active commuting, the following section presents correlation results for **active transport only**, allowing for a clearer understanding of how environmental factors influence exclusively active movement.

Figure 4 shows that active physical activity during school transportation is strongly influenced by environmental characteristics associated with urban density and traffic exposure. The strongest statistically significant correlations were observed with sidewalk area ($r = 0.56, p < 0.001$), accidents with light injuries ($r = 0.56, p < 0.001$), and accidents involving pedestrians ($r = 0.55, p < 0.001$). These strong positive associations demonstrate that higher levels of active school transport occur in areas with extensive pedestrian infrastructure, where children are more exposed to traffic interactions and associated risks. A moderately strong and statistically significant correlation was also found with average daily traffic volume ($r = 0.41, p = 0.006$), indicating that active commuting is more prevalent in traffic-intense urban environments.

Active transportation further showed moderate non-significant positive trends with the number of buildings ($r = 0.29, p = 0.058$) and average building height ($r = 0.26, p = 0.095$), suggesting a tendency for higher active mobility in built-up areas, though these associations did not reach statistical significance. A weak positive but non-significant association was found with average weighted noise ($r = 0.18, p = 0.239$), which may reflect increased noise exposure typical of urban environments where active transport is more common. Greenery showed a weak positive and non-significant correlation ($r = 0.17, p = 0.28$), suggesting that natural environment is not a strong determinant of active transport in this context.

In contrast, active school transport was not associated with sleep indicators, as correlations with sleep efficiency ($r = -0.05, p = 0.74$) and total sleep duration ($r = 0.03, p = 0.83$) were very weak and statistically non-significant. Similarly, MVPA adjusted to 24 h demonstrated only a weak and non-significant correlation with active transportation ($r = 0.26, p = 0.088$), indicating that total daily physical activity does not

fully reflect movement accumulated specifically during the school travel.

Taken together, Figure 4 highlights that active school transportation is strongly conditioned by features of the built environment, particularly pedestrian infrastructure and traffic exposure, while sleep behavior and overall physical activity remain largely independent of these environmental characteristics. These findings underscore the role of local environmental context as a determinant of transport-specific physical activity in children.

3.3. Behavioral profiles of schools (context for environmental analysis)

To provide additional context for interpreting the environmental analysis, we explored whether distinct behavioral profiles exist across schools based on activity and sleep indicators. Up to this point, the analysis was conducted at an aggregate level across all schools, but activity and sleep indicators suggest that meaningful differences may exist between schools and their student populations. Therefore, to capture these differences more precisely, a **cluster analysis** was conducted to classify schools according to the activity and sleep behavior of their students, allowing the identification of distinct lifestyle groups ranging from more active to less active school populations. The analysis revealed three clear clusters (Figure 5), each representing a unique behavioral profile among the participating schools.

The **first cluster** (blue) was characterized by the lowest levels of daily MVPA and transport-related activity, while simultaneously exhibiting the longest sleep duration. This pattern can be interpreted as a sedentary lifestyle with extended sleep, potentially indicating a compensatory mechanism whereby low daytime movement is accompanied by increased rest.

The **second cluster** (green) represented a balanced lifestyle profile. Students in these schools demonstrated moderate to high levels of MVPA in both overall daily activity and active transport to school, alongside high sleep efficiency and optimal sleep duration. This cluster reflects a favorable behavioral pattern consistent with a healthy and well-regulated lifestyle.

The **third cluster** (orange) was defined by the highest engagement in active transportation and MVPA. Despite these positive activity levels, students in this cluster exhibited slightly lower sleep efficiency, suggesting suboptimal nocturnal recovery. This profile can be described as an active transport lifestyle associated with reduced sleep quality.

Together, these findings demonstrate that students exhibit distinct lifestyle profiles, highlighting meaningful heterogeneity in physical activity and sleep behaviors across schools. This underscores the

Figure 4. Correlation between the level of physical activity and environmental factors (dark-green rectangle highlights the relevant correlation block).

Figure 5. Cluster distribution of schools based on physical activity and sleep characteristics.

importance of considering both daytime activity and sleep characteristics when evaluating children's overall health-related behaviors.

4. Discussion

The results of this study show that the level of physical activity during school travel (transport-specific MVPA) is positively associated with urban infrastructure, particularly sidewalk area, traffic intensity, and the number of pedestrian-related traffic accidents. This pattern confirms earlier evidence indicating that dense, well-connected urban environments promote walking and cycling by offering more extensive pedestrian infrastructure, even though they simultaneously expose children to higher traffic volumes and risks (Broberg & Sarjala, 2015; Dessing et al., 2016; Helbich et al., 2016). In contrast, overall daily physical activity and sleep indicators showed no statistically significant associations with environmental variables. This is consistent with previous research suggesting that the built environment tends to influence specific segments of movement behavior – such as active school transport – more strongly than total daily activity levels (Campos-Garzón et al., 2024; Vorlíček et al., 2024).

The influence of greenery appeared inconsistent, reflecting prior evidence that vegetation alone is not necessarily a key driver of active school travel unless combined with safe and continuous pedestrian networks (Khanian et al., 2024). The identified 'urban exposure cluster' – characterized by taller buildings, higher traffic intensity, noise, and accident density – mirrors similar spatial co-occurrence of environmental stressors documented in Finnish and Dutch contexts (Helbich et al., 2016; Sarjala et al., 2016). Between-school variability was more pronounced in environmental indicators than in behavioral ones: while the physical environment differed markedly among schools, transport-specific MVPA and sleep parameters were relatively homogeneous.

The clustering analysis also provides additional context for interpreting the environmental results by identifying behavioral differences between schools based on activity and sleep indicators. The detected school clusters primarily represent differences in behavioral profiles rather than environmental conditions. The clustering results further suggest that although environmental characteristics structure transport-specific MVPA, children's overall activity and sleep profiles form relatively independent behavioral domains. This indicates that while the built environment may facilitate opportunities for active commuting, broader lifestyle-related factors may also influence children's engagement in active school travel.

Beyond the analytical findings, the results also have direct practical relevance. The spatial outputs and behavioral indicators were shared with the participating schools and the city administration, providing a detailed evidence base for evaluating children's mobility patterns and environmental conditions along school routes. The resulting maps and datasets are already being used by the municipality to support planning decisions related to pedestrian infrastructure, traffic safety measures, and safer school travel routes. A major strength of this study lies in the integration of objective accelerometer measurements (ActiGraph), web-mapped school routes, and detailed GIS-based environmental data. This spatially explicit approach provides a detailed perspective on the relationship between the built environment and physical activity, consistent with the along-route exposure framework (Dessing et al. (2016) and Stewart et al. (2017)).

Nevertheless, several limitations must be acknowledged. The analysis was cross-sectional and based on a relatively small sample of eighth-grade pupils ($n = 161$, 10 schools), limiting generalizability and causal inference. School routes were collected via online mapping rather than continuous GPS tracking. Although prior studies (Stewart et al., 2017) have demonstrated high spatial agreement between mapped and GPS routes when narrow buffers are used, minor inaccuracies in route geometry cannot be excluded. Spatiotemporal assignment of MVPA to specific route segments was available only for part of the dataset; extending the number of valid records and improving the precision of travel diary entries would allow a more accurate distinction between movement during school travel and other daily activities. The choice of buffer value and service area size (25 and 500 m) is consistent with international standards, but it remains a methodological assumption that may influence effect sizes. Furthermore, socio-economic and perceptual variables, including parental safety perceptions, were not explicitly modeled, even though literature shows that these factors substantially modify the relationship between environment and behavior (Savolainen et al., 2024; Timperio et al., 2025). Finally, while accelerometer data were processed using standard 24-hour adjustment procedures, classification of time segments may still affect estimates of MVPA associated with school travel.

The findings highlight a complex interaction between opportunity and exposure: the same dense urban environments that provide rich pedestrian infrastructure also present higher levels of traffic and accident risk. This duality aligns with previous work (Broberg & Sarjala, 2015; Ross et al., 2020). The weak associations between overall MVPA, sleep characteristics, and environmental variables further indicate that these behavioral domains are likely

shaped by individual and family-level routines rather than by external spatial conditions (Campos-Garzón et al., 2024; Timperio et al., 2025). Green space seems to play a secondary role in determining school travel behavior, but integration of greenery with safe and direct routes may increase the attractiveness of walking environments.

Despite its limitations, this study demonstrates the feasibility and value of integrating behavioral and spatial data to evaluate active school travel in a medium-sized Central European city.

5. Conclusion

This study set out to determine whether children attending schools located in more walkable, infrastructure-rich, and densely built urban areas accumulate higher levels of MVPA during school travel. **The results clearly support this hypothesis.** Transport-specific MVPA was consistently and positively associated with sidewalk coverage, traffic intensity, and pedestrian-related traffic accidents along school routes, demonstrating that compact and well-connected urban environments facilitate active movement during school commuting.

In contrast, overall daily MVPA and sleep characteristics showed no meaningful associations with environmental determinants, suggesting that whole-day behavioral patterns are shaped primarily by individual, social, or household routines rather than by the spatial structure of the school environment.

While transport-specific MVPA grouped schools along an environmental gradient, sleep-related indicators produced a distinctly different clustering structure. Schools with the most active transport profiles did not exhibit the most favorable sleep patterns, and vice versa. This indicates that sleep duration and sleep efficiency are only weakly related to environmental exposure and instead reflect individual, familial, or socio-behavioral routines that lie outside the direct influence of urban form. Taken together, the clusters show that physical activity and sleep represent two independent lifestyle domains that respond to different sets of determinants.

By integrating mapped school routes with accelerometer-measured MVPA and detailed GIS-based environmental indicators, this study provides rare, spatially explicit evidence from a Central European context. The findings highlight that active school travel is the behavioral domain most sensitive to environmental exposure, whereas movement within the school surroundings and whole-day activity remain relatively stable across contrasting urban contexts.

Beyond the analytical contribution, the results also have practical relevance. The spatial datasets and map outputs generated in this study were shared with the municipality and participating schools and are already

being used as an evidence base for evaluating children's mobility patterns and planning improvements in pedestrian infrastructure, traffic safety measures, and safer school routes.

Software

All analytical results (spatial data and maps) presented in this paper were processed, managed, processed and created in the Esri platform ArcGIS Pro. Statistical analysis was done in RStudio. Graphic components were designed in Adobe Illustrator software and incorporated into the final map layout.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17668838> (Burian et al., 2025).

References

- Althoff, T., Ivanovic, B., King, A. C., Hicks, J. L., Delp, S. L., & Leskovec, J. (2025). Countrywide natural experiment links built environment to physical activity. *Nature*, 634(8017), 125–132. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09321-3>
- Aranda-Balboa, M. J., Huertas-Delgado, F. J., Herrador-Colmenero, M., Cardon, G., & Chillón, P. (2020). Parental barriers to active transport to school: A systematic review. *International Journal of Public Health*, 65(1), 87–98. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-019-01313-1>
- Broberg, A., Salminen, S., & Kytä, M. (2013). Physical environmental characteristics promoting independent and active transport to children's meaningful places. *Applied Geography*, 38, 43–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2012.11.014>
- Broberg, A., & Sarjala, S. (2015). School travel mode choice and the urban structure of the neighbourhoods. *Transport Policy*, 37, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2014.10.011>
- Burian, J., Macků, K., Zimmermannová, J., & Nėtek, R. (2020). Sustainable spatial and temporal development of land prices: A case study of Czech cities. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(6), 396. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi9060396>
- Burian, J., & Šramo, B. (2024). *Safe journey to school 2023 [web map application]*. Palacký University Olomouc, Department of Geoinformatics. <https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/fc98b552be8c4afb8ac8d52a87575c81>
- Burian, J., Vorlíček, M., Dygrýn, J., & Panek, J. (2025). *Dataset: Environmental influences on children's active travel: A spatial analysis of school routes* [Data set]. Zenodo.
- Campos-Garzón, P., Stewart, T., Palma-Leal, X., Molina-García, J., Herrador-Colmenero, M., Schipperijn, J., Chillón, P., & Barranco-Ruiz, Y. (2024). Are Spanish adolescents who actively commute to and from school more active in other domains? A spatiotemporal investigation. *Health & Place*, 86, 103211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2024.103211>
- Carver, A., Timperio, A., & Crawford, D. (2019). How are the built environment and household travel characteristics associated with children's active transport in Melbourne, Australia? *Journal of Transport & Health*, 12, 22–31.
- City of Olomouc. (2024). *Summary report on primary and nursery schools established by the City of Olomouc for the 2024/2025 school year*. https://www.olomouc.eu/administrace/repository/gallery/articles/11_/11327/souhrnna-zprava-o-zs-a-ms-2024-2025.doc
- Crooks, N., Alston, L., Nichols, M., Bolton, K. A., Allender, S., Fraser, P., Le, H., Bliss, J., Rennie, C., Orellana, L., & Strugnell, C. (2021). Association between the school physical activity environment, measured and self-reported student physical activity and active transport behaviours in Victoria, Australia. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 18(1), 79. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-021-01151-6>
- Czech Statistical Office. (2021). *Commuting to and from work and schools based on the 2021 census results Praha: ČSÚ*. <https://csu.gov.cz/produkty/vyjizdka-a-dojizdka-do-zamestnani-a-skol-podle-vysledku-scitani-lidu-2021>
- Dalton, M. A., Longacre, M. R., Drake, K. M., Gibson, L., Adachi-Mejia, A. M., Swain, K., Xie, H., & Owens, P. M. (2011). Built environment predictors of active travel to school among adolescents. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 41(4), 470–475.
- Dessing, D., de Vries, S. I., Hegeman, G., Verhagen, E., van Mechelen, W., & Pierik, F. H. (2016). Children's route choice during active transportation to school: Differences between shortest and actual route. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 13(1), 48. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-016-0373-y>
- Dygrýn, J., Mitáš, J., Gába, A., Rubín, L., & Frömel, K. (2015). Changes in active commuting to school in Czech adolescents in different types of built environment across a 10-year period. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 12(10), 12988–12998. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph121012988>
- Helbich, M. (2017). Children's school commuting in the Netherlands: Does it matter how urban form is incorporated in mode choice models? *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, 11(7), 507–517. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2016.1275892>
- Helbich, M., Emmichoven, M. J. Z. v., Dijst, M. J., Kwan, M.-P., Pierik, F. H., & Vries, S. I. d. (2016). Natural and built environmental exposures on children's active school travel: A Dutch GPS-based cross-sectional study. *Health & Place*, 39, 101–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2016.03.003>
- Hunter, R. F., Cleland, C., Trott, M., O'Neill, S., Küçükali, H., Mullineaux, S., Kee, F., McKinley, J. M., Neville, C., O'Hara, L., Marr, C., McAlinden, M., Ellis, G., McKnight, A., Schipperijn, J., McHugh Power, J., Duong, T., & McGuinness, B. (2024). Integrating accelerometer, GPS, GIS and molecular data to investigate mechanistic pathways of the urban environmental exposure and cognitive outcomes. *BMJ Open*, 14(12), e085318. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2024-085318>
- Jacobs, J., Crooks, N., Allender, S., Strugnell, C., Backholer, K., & Nichols, M. (2021). Is the physical activity environment surrounding primary schools associated with students' weight status, physical activity or active transport? *BMJ Open*, 11(7), e045785. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-045785>
- Khanian, M., Łaskiewicz, E., & Kronenberg, J. (2024). Exposure to greenery during children's home-school walks: Socio-economic inequalities in alternative routes. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 130, 104162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2024.104162>
- Larsen, K., Gilliland, J., Hess, P., Tucker, P., Irwin, J., & He, M. (2012). The influence of the built environment and parental perceptions on children's mode of travel to school. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 102(2), 357–373. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00045608.2011.627059>
- McDonald, N. C. (2008). Critical factors for active transportation to school among low-income and minority students: Evidence from the 2001 National Household Travel Survey. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 34(4), 341–344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2008.01.004>
- Migueles, J. H., Rowlands, A. V., Huber, F., Sabia, S., & van Hees, V. T. (2019). GGIR: A research community-driven open source R package for generating physical activity and sleep outcomes from multi-day raw accelerometer data. *Journal for the Measurement of Physical*

- Behaviour*, 2(3), 188–196. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jmpb.2018-0063>
- Nigg, C. R., Allothman, S. A., Alghannam, A. F., Schipperijn, J., AlAhmed, R., Alsukait, R. F., Rakic, S., Cetinkaya, V., Al-Hazzaa, H. M., & Alqahtani, S. A. (2024). A systematic review on the associations between the built environment and physical activity in tropical or desert climate regions. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 21(1), 101. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-024-01582-x>
- Olomouc City Chief Architect's Office. (2024). *Safe journey to school 2023: Project evaluation*. Statutární město Olomouc. https://kam.olomouc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/bezpecna_cesta_do_skoly_2023_fn.pdf
- Panter, J. R., Jones, A. P., van Sluijs, E. M. F., & Griffin, S. J. (2008). Neighborhood, route, and school environments and children's active commuting. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 5(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-5-34>
- Rojas Lopez, M. C., & Wong, Y. D. (2017). Children's active trips to school: A review and analysis. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 4(2), 125–142.
- Ross, A., Godwyll, J., & Adams, M. (2020). The moderating effect of distance on features of the built environment and active school transport. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(21), 7856. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17217856>
- Rypl, O., Macků, K., & Pászto, V. (2024). The quality of life in Czech rural and urban spaces. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 43. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02423-1>
- Sarjala, S., Broberg, A., & Hirvonen, J. (2016). School travel mode choice and urban form: The role of the built environment. *Journal of Transport and Land Use*, 9(2), 143–158.
- Savolainen, E., Lindqvist, A.-K., Mikaelsson, K., Nyberg, L., & Rutberg, S. (2024). Children's active school transportation: An international scoping review of psychosocial factors. *Systematic Reviews*, 13(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-023-02414-y>
- Stewart, T., Schipperijn, J., Snizek, B., & Duncan, S. (2017). Adolescent school travel: Comparing on-line mapped versus GPS-measured routes and environmental exposures. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 5, 112–124.
- Timperio, A., Ball, K., Salmon, J., Roberts, R., Giles-Corti, B., Simmons, D., Baur, L., & Crawford, D. (2006). Personal, family, social, and environmental correlates of active commuting to school. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 30(1), 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2005.08.047>
- Timperio, A., Duncan, S., Akram, M., Molina-García, J., Van Dyck, D., Barnett, A., Salonna, F., Anjana RM, Sallis, J. F., Vorlíček, M., Hinckson, E., Cain, K. L., Conway, T. L., Wan Muda, WAM., Moran, M., Oyeyemi, A. L., Pizarro, A., Reis, R. S., Rezwan, S. M., Schipperijn, J., ... Cerin, E. (2025). Associations between parental perceptions of neighbourhood environments and active travel to school: IPEN Adolescent study. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 22(1), 55. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-025-01738-3>
- Vorlíček, M., Burian, J., Stewart, T., Dygrýn, J., Rubín, L., Mitáš, J., Duncan, S., Schipperijn, J., & Pratt, M. (2024). Where are Czech adolescents active? The patterns of movement and transport behavior in different active living domains. *Journal of Physical Activity & Health*, 21(6), 586–594. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2023-0212>
- Vorlíček, M., Dygrýn, J., Janda, D., Voráčová, J., Duncan, S., Sigmund, E., & Sigmundová, D. (2025). Raising active children: How family and school shape health-promoting physical activity—findings from the FAMIPASS study. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 7, 1530398.
- Wangzom, D., White, M., & Paay, J. (2023). Perceived safety influencing active travel to school – a built environment perspective. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(2), 1026. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20021026>
- Wex, I., Geserick, M., Leibert, T., Igel, U., Sobek, C., Meigen, C., Kiess, W., & Vogel, M. (2023). Active school transport in an urban environment: Prevalence and perceived barriers. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), 557. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15464-7>
- Wong, B. Y. M., Faulkner, G., & Buliung, R. (2011). GIS-measured environmental correlates of active school transport: A systematic review of 14 studies. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 8(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-8-39>